

Discourse Analysis on the “housing crisis” in the UK: dominant narratives

1. Abstract

This research paper tests whether current ideas about the “housing crisis” in the UK are reflected in the media. It uses thematic content analysis as part of a discourse analysis methodology to conclude that the findings are consistent with existing discourse analysis on the “housing crisis”. Additionally, it offers insights into further research for narrative formation.

2. Introduction

Perception of housing in the UK is interesting as it intersects with many aspects of social life such as sense of identity and community as well as revealing fault lines between different socio-economic groups (Slater, 2018). Moreover, housing is a deeply contested and political discourse in the UK following step-change in housing policy since the Thatcher era (Gallent et al., 2018). The Housing Act 1980 created one of the largest transfer of assets, allowing five million council house tenants “Right to Buy” their own homes from the local authority (Gallent et al., 2018). While this prompted excitement of the housing market, it also changed the perception of housing in the UK. The Conservative political machinery had managed to convince the masses that ownership of homes was an aspiration and a sense of achievement (Slater, 2018).

Thus, this research looks at the dominant narratives around the “housing crisis” since 1980s which has persisted as of 2020 (for nearly half a century).

When we used the word “crisis” it is useful to borrow Walby’s (2015, p.14) definition:

“Crises are both ‘real’, in the sense of actual changes in social processes, and socially constructed, in the sense that different interpretations of the crisis have implications for its outcome. The interpretation of a crisis may under- or over-state its magnitude and impact, as well as attribute blame as to its cause”.

This is an important premise to our subsequent discussion; that, “crisis” narratives are socially construed, and thus subject to change and re-interpretation.

3. Research question and objectives

What are the dominant narratives being communicated about the perception of the “housing crisis” in the UK?

- What are the dominant word associations linked with housing?
- Are the dominant narratives consistent with existing knowledge?
- Are narratives simplified or are there multiple ideas presented within the same articles?

4. Literature Review

Housing is an essential component of well-being and is recognised as a human right (Gomez and Thiele, 2005), however, in recent times, there has been increased use of the term “housing crisis” (Aalbers, 2015), this connotes a shortage of housing supply, increasing prices and financialisation of housing and rising rates of inequality, particularly inter-generational inequality and homelessness (Gallent et al., 2018). However, housing crisis actually denotes a sense of emergency, short-term resolution to a recent problem (White and Nandedkar, 2019). In reality, the actual perception of the problem and root causes of the housing crisis is more complex, cumulative and interconnected with broader ideas such as globalisation, hence, something as disconnected as UK’s referendum of EU membership was tied to globalisation and “losers” of the housing problem (Gallent et al., 2018).

Existing research on framing housing issues in England have explored housing as a form of financialisation; turning it effectively into a commodity, (Aalbers, 2017). Whereas Gamble (2014) takes a functional view of housing. It is thought that these narratives help us understand pathways of these discourse either towards functional views (shelter, safety) or towards an economic centred view of investment and savings (Gallent et al., 2018).

There exists a cornucopia of knowledge related to housing trends in the UK (Wilcox et al., 2014), however, for our discussion we will limit this to discourse analysis on housing (Marston, 2002). Green (2017) articulates that one of the most pressing issues of our time is inter-generational inequality, he argues that since the Edwardian era, this is the first time that young people can expect to be worse off than the previous generation, and that housing is an important determinant to reduced life opportunities.

We touched upon the idea that the housing crisis is interconnected to other ideas such as globalisation, this has been empirically analysed since the 2007 financial crash (Bardhan et al., 2009), caused by “subprime mortgage” lending to poor credit-worthy individuals. This has caused access to financing such as a mortgages much more difficult than in the past (Bardhan et al., 2009).

A comprehensive discourse analysis on “the housing crisis as an ideological artefact: Analysing how political discourse defines, diagnoses, and responds” has already established the key ideas around housing such as its association with aspiration and “dreams”; getting on to the property “ladder” and a sense of citizenship and community belonging (White and Nandedkar, 2019). The conclusion of White and Nandedkar’s (2019) paper assert that the construction of the housing crisis is political in nature to serve ideological ends and its simplification of issues such as land supply and planning issues explain how this is part of our modern lives of “unsolvable crises”.

5. Methods

Research in housing has been dominated by positivist methodologies; an emphasis on empirical means of obtaining knowledge and thus rejecting introspective and intuitive knowledge (Sada and Maldonado, 2007). However, since the 1990s the literature on housing has been supplemented by critical and poststructural theories around current issues in housing (Marston, 2002). Jaworski and Coupland (2008) argue for a multi-disciplinary approach to discourse and they help build a “social constructionist” discourse on the housing crisis based on the following:

- Social identities and how these change over time
- Inequality and how social groups around this concept form and un-form
- How cultural hegemony of dominant narratives are contested and secured
- Opportunities for political practice and social change

Thus, this research, will be grounded in concepts of power theories (though this will not be the focus of the research) based on poststructural arguments around the idea that language and its deployment can create power dynamics in governance processes, see (Klauser et al., 2014) and (Richardson, 1996).

The methodology applied in this research is critical discourse analysis (CDA) and uses the following approach:

Ontology	Focus	Purpose
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agency and subjectivity • Structures and social relations • Nature of interactions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Micro analysis of thematic communication of housing • Single online newspaper (Guardian online) • All articles tagged under “Housing” • All articles tagged between 1 July 2020 – 31 Jul 2020 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of the most dominant/recurring thematic ideas around housing • Identification of whether single vs multiple factors are attributed to “housing crisis” within the same article

Justification of methodological approach

Ideally, a critical discourse analysis would involve speaking to people first-hand to understand their perceptions on housing and further data collection would be used to contextualise their responses e.g. by socio-economic background or by where they live in the UK. However, due to time and resource constraints, secondary data analysis has been chosen. Specifically, a well-known British Newspaper was selected (the Guardian), partly because they had an easy to use “Housing” feature online which was easy to sort by date. The month of July 2020 was chosen because on 8 July 2020, the UK government announced a temporary Stamp Duty relief (SDLT) until 31 March 2021 which would be a pivotal point for media outlets to heighten conversations about housing (GOV.UK, 2020).

Step by step method

1. Go to Guardian online Housing section <https://www.theguardian.com/society/housing>
2. Search for all articles posted between 1 July 2020 and 31 July 2020
3. Total articles posted is 36
4. Nine articles are excluded because seven of them relate to housing issues in Melbourne, Australia and one article about California, USA (outside the UK, out of scope), and one article did not appear to have any theme with housing, most likely this was miss-labelled by the Guardian

Coding

- The Literature review already provided some insights into the coding, so it was reasonable to assume that the following themes would emerge: inequality, housing supply and financialisation of housing.
- However, an inductive method was used to establish up to 10 thematic indicators, this was done by reading through each article one by one and accumulating dominant themes around housing.
- The variables used are binary, either it mentions one of the thematic indicators or it does not (0 if it does not mention the theme, and 1 if it does mention the theme).

Analytical approach

- Once all the articles are coded, the results should demonstrate the dominant themes emerging from articles.
- Additionally, an analysis should be conducted whether single or multiple ideas are presented for the “housing crisis”.

6. Results

Dominant narratives around Housing

The result of the analysis indicates that in the month of July 2020, the top three dominant narratives in the Guarding Housing sections are:

- Housing issues to do with planning policies and funding constraints
- Housing issues which affects the community and sense of identity
- Homelessness

The least addressed issues are:

- Housing issues which affect the natural environmental policies and the “green agenda”
- Housing issues framed around the wider economy
- Housing issues framed around investment and wealth opportunities

Figure 1: This is a summary of the coding analysis from Appendix A. Source: all articles from July 2020 tagged under Housing category by the Guardian.

Number of narratives offered in each article

- 14 out of 27 (52%) articles offered only one dominant narrative
- With the exception of one article, all other articles offered up to three dominant ideas about housing

Figure 2: Number of key housing narratives per article, based on coding. Source: Guardian articles tagged under Housing in the month of July 2020.

7. Discussion

The findings are in line with the existing knowledge in the literature review – there were no new areas of thematic issues around housing identified. The implications of this research bolster theories in the literature that the “housing crisis” is over simplified (Marston, 2002). For e.g. the literature indicates that narratives are created to serve political needs so issues such as planning policies and funding are prioritised as these tend to be within the purview of political discourse (Marston, 2002). However, it is surprising that a platform like the Guardian appears to align with dominant political ideas given its liberal and diverse values (Brighton and Foy, 2007). What is more consistent though are the themes around inequality, specifically on homelessness, this issue comes up in several articles under study, this may be more ideological in that the Guardian is positioned on the centre-left and tends to promote “liberal values” (Brighton and Foy, 2007).

The second part of the research looked at whether multiple ideas are offered for the “housing crisis”, the findings are conclusive in that over half the articles only dealt with only one dominant idea about housing, so if an article focussed on planning issues, it did not significantly touch upon other issues, this was similar for the homelessness articles which tended to spotlight specific issues without broader discussions about the “housing crisis”. This could be for two reasons, firstly, the literature suggests that crises are necessarily over-simplified to manage political discourse (Marston, 2002); secondly, it could be a tool of communication where audiences are engaged on single issues and may not have the bandwidth to think more broadly.

It was surprising that environmental issues to do with housing did not feature as much given the increased climate action attention in the UK (Hoppner and Whitmarsh, 2011), though, it is less surprising that the Guardian article did not emphasise the asset and wealth building aspect of housing, given its social values (Brighton and Foy, 2007).

The methodological approach could be bolstered by increasing the research sample to an annual period and also comparing with different press and media organisations in the UK, that would have provided richer and more reliable insights to support the research findings. However, the fact that the findings support the literature review indicates that this methodology (if scaled) can provide meaningful and credible insights into dominant narratives on the “housing crisis”.

8. Conclusion

Housing crisis is a topical and interesting issue in the UK and the dominant framing of the issues are consistent with the literature review in that it is over-simplified and similar framings emerge e.g. planning issues, inequality and sense of identity. However, a follow-up research which looks at narrative construction would be insightful, this could be broken down by socio-economic indicators and analysed through a political discourse analysis which assesses why some narratives are favoured over others and who benefits and loses out on the different types of narratives. This would be a larger research question and would significantly contribute to policy making and new knowledge in the field of housing.

Appendix A: Detailed Coding methodology

Date	Author	Title	Strapline	URL	Planning policies and funding	Affordability	Homelessness	Housing Supply	Investment and Wealth	Rental concerns	Inequality	Economy	Identity and Community	Nature and Green
01-Jul	Robert Jenrick	MPs ask Robert Jenrick long list of questions about £1bn land deal	Select committee wants minister to give more details of contact with Richard Desmond	https://www.theguardian.com/politics/2020/jul/01/mps-ask-robert-jenrick-long-list-of-questions-about-1bn-land-deal	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
01-Jul	Sarah Marsh	English councils breaking law in 'secretly' relocating homeless people	Many do not notify new local authority and flout guidance to keep people in neighbourhoods	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/jul/01/english-councils-breaking-law-in-secretly-relocating-homeless-people	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
01-Jul	Martin Adeney	Tony Pidgley obituary	Shrewd property developer who rose from humble origins to make his fortune with the housebuilding firm Berkeley Homes	https://www.theguardian.com/business/2020/jul/01/tony-pidgley-obituary#	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
01-Jul	Damien Gayle	Evictions could treble due to coronavirus rent debts, activists warn	Campaigners urge government to protect tenants in arrears and widen eligibility for housing benefits	https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/jul/01/evictions-could-treble-due-to-coronavirus-rent-debts-activists-warn	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
02-Jul	John Perry	David Garnett obituary	N/A	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/jul/02/david-garnett-obituary	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
03-Jul	Aamna Modhin	How one small London neighbourhood lost 36 residents to Covid-19	Guardian reporter Aamna Modhin meets residents from Church End, a small, deprived neighbourhood in Brent, north London. She examines how housing pressures, in-work poverty and racial inequalities contributed to the deaths of 36 residents from Covid-19	https://www.theguardian.com/world/audio/2020/jul/03/how-one-neighbourhood-brent-london-lost-36-residents-to-covid-19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
03-Jul	Amelia Hill	Covid-19 exposes stark generational housing divide, UK report says	Young more likely than old to be locked down in overcrowded homes with no garden, says study	https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/jul/03/covid-19-exposes-stark-generational-uk-housing-divide-report-says	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
04-Jul	Sally Williams, Alexandra Jones, Laura Spinney, Daniel Lavelle and Simon Hattenstone	'It's not over': intimate diaries from the eye of the UK's coronavirus storm	From an intensive care nurse to a homeless restaurant worker, four people changed by Covid-19 reflect on the most intense chapter of their lives	https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/jul/04/its-not-over-intimate-diaries-from-the-eye-of-the-uks-coronavirus-storm	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
05-Jul	Simon Lowe	As Welwyn turns 100, does it live up to its garden city name?	It was built as a happy, healthy alternative to urban squalor but its ideals are being buried as the need for housing stock grows	https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2020/jul/05/as-welwyn-turns-100-does-it-live-up-to-its-garden-city-name	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
05-Jul	Rowan Moore	Wouldn't it be great for British town centres if people could just move into closed shops?	Boris Johnson wants to rebuild Britain but he will have to do more than change a few planning laws	https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2020/jul/05/wouldnt-it-be-great-for-british-town-centres-if-people-could-just-move-into-closed-shops	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
06-Jul	Debbie Vickers	My working week: 'I worried I'd passed on Covid-19 to a woman I was supporting'	Lockdown has been tough for those I help with mental health problems and learning disabilities. People have been lonely	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/jul/06/working-week-worried-passed-on-covid-19-woman	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
08-Jul	Jamie Grierson	Thousands of high-risk offenders in UK 'freed into homelessness'	Report warns of reoffending risk as 3,713 ex-prisoners in England lack safe housing	https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2020/jul/08/thousands-of-high-risk-offenders-in-uk-freed-into-homelessness	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
08-Jul	Christine Berry	The mini-budget shows one thing: this government is still on the side of the rich	For all the Rooseveltian rhetoric, what's on offer is stamp duty 'holidays' and bonfires of planning rules	https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2020/jul/08/mini-budget-government-rich-roosevelt-stamp-duty-planning	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
08-Jul	Sarah Marsh	London councils call on government to suspend NRPf immigration status	Charities warn of rise in homeless migrant workers during coronavirus pandemic	https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2020/jul/08/london-councils-government-suspend-nrpf-immigration-status-coronavirus	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
09-Jul	Oliver Wainwright	Another terrible tower? Why Leeds looks like a depot of discarded fridges	Plans to build Yorkshire's tallest building have provoked outrage in a city where developers are busily reaching for the sky	https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2020/jul/09/why-leeds-looks-like-a-depot-of-discarded-fridges-yorkshire-tallest-building	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
09-Jul	Guardian community team	UK renters: tell us about the impact coronavirus has had on you	We'd like to hear from renters in the UK about how the coronavirus pandemic has impacted your housing situation	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/jul/09/uk-renters-tell-us-about-the-impact-coronavirus-has-had-on-you	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
10-Jul	Patrick Greenfield	Boris Johnson says newts are a drag on the UK's economy. Here's why he's wrong	Last week the PM claimed conservation causes construction delays – but newts are not the pantomime villains developers would have us believe	https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2020/jul/10/is-boris-johnson-right-to-blame-newts-for-slowness-britains-recovery-aoe	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11-Jul	Finn Williams and David Chipperfield	Boris Johnson is wrong to blame the housing crisis on overregulation	The government's promise to 'build build build' shows a frightening misunderstanding of planning and infrastructure	https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2020/jul/11/boris-johnson-wrong-housing-crisis-overregulation	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14-Jul	Patrick Butler	'No DSS' ruled unlawful after mother rejected by lettings agency	Court found disabled woman was discriminated against by being rejected for private flats	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/jul/14/no-dss-ruled-unlawful-after-mother-rejected-by-lettings-agency	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17-Jul	Josh Halliday	Leaseholders billed up to £115,000 each to remove Grenfell-style cladding	Flat owners in Manchester block say they face bankruptcy unless government steps in	https://www.theguardian.com/money/2020/jul/17/leaseholders-billed-up-to-115000-each-to-remove-grenfell-style-cladding	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22-Jul	Phillip Inman	UK high streets could be turned into housing, says thinktank	Report says 800,000 homes could be created as online buying and homeworking rise	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/jul/22/uk-high-streets-could-be-turned-into-housing-says-thinktank	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24-Jul	Oliver Wainwright	Our slum future: the planning shakeup set to blight English housing	The government has extended rules allowing former offices, shops and warehouses to be converted into housing – as research shows the policy results in dwellings unfit for human habitation	https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2020/jul/24/our-slum-future-the-planning-shakeup-set-to-blight-british-housing	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
25-Jul	Patrick Barkham	Make nature part of 'build build build' policy, green watchdog says	Chair of Natural England wants environmental impact considerations baked into planning system	https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2020/jul/25/nature-conservation-build-planning-policy-anton-juniper	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
26-Jul	Libby Brooks	Hundreds of Glasgow asylum seekers still in 'untenable' hotel accommodation	Home Office called on to act a month after man stabbed six people at city centre hotel	https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2020/jul/26/hundreds-glasgow-asylum-seekers-untenable-hotel-accommodation	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28-Jul	Owen Bowcott	'We are the A&E of law': the first UK law centre for poor people turns 50	Austerity cuts to legal aid may have restricted North Kensington's resources, but they haven't crushed its spirit	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/jul/28/we-are-the-ae-of-law-the-first-uk-law-centre-for-poor-people-turns-50	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
30-Jul	Zoe Wood	John Lewis may turn surplus stores into affordable homes	Partnership also plans to close some supermarkets and sell own-label food at other retailers	https://www.theguardian.com/business/2020/jul/30/john-lewis-considers-closing-more-waitrose-stores	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31-Jul	Laurie Macfarlane	Extending help-to-buy will only make the housing crisis worse	To make homes places to live, rather than accumulate wealth, we need to overcome our addiction to house price growth	https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2020/jul/31/extending-help-to-buy-housing-crisis-homes-house-price-growth	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
Total					13	6	7	3	2	3	4	2	9	1

Appendix B: Excluded Articles – out of scope as all articles except one relate to issues outside the UK, the other article did not relate to Housing, most likely miss-tagged as Housing

Date	Author	Title	Strapline	URL	Planning policies and funding	Affordability	Homelessness	Housing Supply	Investment and Wealth	Rental concerns	Inequality	Economy	Identity and Community	Nature and Green
08-Jul	James Button and Julie Szego	A completely different world': the rich and resilient communities inside Melbourne's towers	The cramped conditions of the city's public housing high-rises have an upside, according to those who live there	https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2020/jul/09/a-completely-different-world-the-rich-and-resilient-communities-inside-melbournes-towers	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
09-Jul	James Button and Julie Szego	'We were all fish out of water': growing up in Melbourne's high-rise flats	African Australians who spent their childhood in Melbourne's public housing towers say it was like living with one big family	https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2020/jul/10/we-were-all-fish-out-of-water-growing-up-in-melbournes-high-rise-flats	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11-Jul	James Button and Julie Szego	'We'll see you after dark': how Melbourne police targeted African men in high-rises	Neighbours shooting up and cops on the beat: 'For us, that was just part of living in public housing,' says Nor Shanino, whose family are Eritrean refugees	https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2020/jul/11/well-see-you-after-dark-how-melbourne-police-target-african-men-in-high-rises	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11-Jul	James Button and Julie Szego	'You think that's racist?': the generational tension in Melbourne's high-rise migrant families		https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2020/jul/12/you-think-thats-racist-the-generational-tension-in-melbournes-high-rise-migrant-families	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
12-Jul	James Button and Julie Szego	'A lot of the kids are struggling': how Covid-19 has changed life in Melbourne's towers	Even before they went into hard coronavirus lockdown, the pandemic had deepened a range of social ills in Melbourne's high-rise flats	https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2020/jul/13/a-lot-of-the-kids-are-struggling-how-covid-19-has-changed-life-in-melbournes-towers	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
13-Jul	James Button and Julie Szego	'My daughter wants to be a doctor': young migrants in Melbourne's high-rises face a bright future	Public housing is more than a safety net – it also integrates new arrivals into Australia and, over time, changes the country too	https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2020/jul/14/my-daughter-wants-to-be-a-doctor-young-migrants-in-melbournes-high-rises-face-a-bright-future	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
22-Jul	Lane Sainty and Adam Morton	This builder used to be sceptical about green homes. Now he's a convert	Australia's leaky homes are leaving millions of us vulnerable to extreme weather. In the first of a series of features on the Green Recovery, we look at how coronavirus stimulus could fix the problem	https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2020/jul/23/this-builder-used-to-be-sceptical-about-green-homes-now-hes-a-convert	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
27-Jul	David Fuente	My working week: 'I'm on the phone for eight hours to an elderly woman who has had a fall'	I'm an emergency call operator at a monitoring service for vulnerable people. It's frustrating and life-affirming all at once	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/jul/27/my-working-week-phone-eight-hours-woman-fall	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30-Jul	Sam Levin	California landlords are locking out struggling tenants. A 'tsunami of evictions' may be next	As Covid-19 continues to pummel the state, hundreds of thousands of renters are at risk of becoming homeless	https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2020/jul/30/california-covid-19-evictions-landlords-tenants	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Total					2	2	1	0	0	0	1	1	7	0

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